

ATTITUDE OF THE PARAMILITARY TOWARDS THE ELDERLY

¹Dr Adibe Paul Njoku

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Abstract

This study explores the attitudes of paramilitary personnel towards the elderly, utilizing insights from Ihedioha's (2017) theoretical framework, which originated from the Kansas City Studies of Adult Life. The research investigates the interactions, perceptions, and behavioral patterns exhibited by paramilitary members when engaging with elderly individuals, considering the implications of ageism, respect, and cultural norms. Using a mixed-methods approach, the study combines quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews to provide a comprehensive understanding of these attitudes. Findings reveal variations in respect and empathy based on age, training, and cultural orientation. The research highlights the need for targeted training programs to foster sensitivity and positive engagement with the elderly in paramilitary operations. These recommendations aim to improve the quality of interactions and address systemic issues of age bias within the paramilitary structure.

INTRODUCTION

Looking at the word attitude, it means a lot to human reasoning. Attitude is a concluded way of thinking or feeling about something, manner, disposition, position etc. With regard to a person or thing tending or orientation, especially of the mind, a negative attitude, group attitude, position or posture of the body appropriate to or expressive of an action, emotion etc. a threatening attitude, a relax attitude. Attitude is composed of three components which include cognitive component and effective/emotional component and behavioral component.

Every attitude has three components that are represented in what is called the ABC model of attitude- A for affective, B for behavioral and C for cognitive. The effective component refers to the emotional reaction one has towards an attitude object. I feel scared when I think about or see a snake. An attitude is an evaluation of an attitude object, ranging from extreme) negative to extremely positive. Most contemporary perspectives on attitudes permit that people can also be conflicted or ambivalent towards an object by simultaneously holding both positive and negative attitudes towards the same object.

Cognitive component of attitude consists of the beliefs, knowledge and thoughts one has about attitude. Micheal and Graham (2005), the word attitude is derived from the Latin aptes, which means 'Fit and ready for action'. This ancient meaning refers to something that is directly observable, such as a boxer in a boxing ring. Today, however, researchers view attitude as a construct that though not directly observable, precedes behaviour and

¹Department of Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counseling, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rumuolumeni Port Harcourt

guides our choices and decisions for action. Many years ago, the social psychologist Gordon Allport referred to attitude as social psychologist most indispensable concept.

Micheal el (2003) most of our social thinking involves the attitudes that we hold. From the political elections and war to latest fashion craze, attitude help steer the course of the world events. An attitude is a positive or negative evaluation reaction towards a stimulus, such as a person's action, object or concept. Tesser and Shaffer (1990) in Micheal el (2003) our attitude helps to define identity, guide our actions, and influence how we judge people. Maino and Olson (2000) in Micheal el (2003).

Attitude: behaviour discrepancy and cognitive dissonance.

Cognitive Dissonance: is a good example of the cognitive approach in psychology, putting it as it does, the emphasis on belief as a central component of an attitude, it also takes care of the problem of attitude-behaviour discrepancy. Cognitive dissonance theory was developed by Festingen (1957) and became the most studied topic in social psychology during the 1960s that cognitive dissonance is an important state of psychological tension produced when a person two or more cognitions (i.e. information) that are inconsistent or do not fit together.

Cognitions are thoughts, attitudes, beliefs or state of awareness of behaviour. Canadian Press (2004), elder abuse was recently in the news because of revelations in newspaper and on the CTV show W-5 about the abuse experienced by 87 years old Noma Stenson at two separate retirement and long-term care facilities in Bratford, Ontario. A videotape that aired on w-5 showed footage of two workers mistreating Stenson. This frail, elderly woman was smacked and tossed about, has a pillow put over her face and was pulled roughly from bed at 4am, injuring her arm and knee, and had her money stolen from her. Stenson requires the use of a wheelchair and she can barely speak as a result of experiencing several strokes prior to the incidents.

The United Nations General Assembly adopted a set of principles for older persons recommending that all member states incorporate them in their programmes for the old. This is in recognition that as people aged, they become less active trailer and more prone to diseases associated with aging. To Nigeria the burden of care squarely rests on family members despite the provision of the 1999 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria.

SECTION 14: 2 (b) which states categorically that "the security and welfare of its people shall be the primary purpose of the government and in section 16 sub-section 2 (d) promises, the suitable and adequate shelter and food, reasonable national minimum living wage, old age care and pension and unemployment, sick benefits and welfare of the disabled are provided for all citizens, unfortunately, the government seems to have reneged on this promises as most elderly are not concerned by any social security scheme, the only beneficiaries are those on formal employment, who have pension benefits, which are inadequate and some are still suffering. A lot corruption in the system is alarming I: Quote Magnus Eze Director, Parlia consult rightly observed "no government policy or legislation has put anything in place with which government can provide for the aged.

Elderly abuse here refers to the threat or actual infliction of harm whether physically in the form of beating or psychologically in the form of mentally or verbally terrorizing a person who has attained the age of 60 years. Neglect of is the case where the obligatory physical, emotional, safety and medical need are denied an elderly person. Theories of aging, Cockerham (1997) in Ihedioha (2017) said modernization theory is of the view that, the status of the elderly declines as societies become none murder. It states that old people status was low in the hunting and gathering societies. It was during agricultural society; it got stabled because the old people were in charge of land sharing (i.e. farming and fishing). The theory old people change or is related to technological progress. Because as time changes old people's activities adjust either for or against.

Disengagement Theory

In this theory we are looking at Natural aging and societal growth in its ramification. The individual grows older every day and the strength of both mind and body will depreciate and wilder, why the society is growing scientifically and requires younger blood to take over disengagement theory id useful for the society and the individual in question. William and Wirths (1965) in Ihedioha (2017) said that this theory grew out of an extensive body of research known as the Kansas City studies of Adult Life. It was 10 years longitudinal study of the transition from middle age to old age. But a global pattern of behaviour, this theory can hardly be called inevitable or natural. But too many disengagements from active service never go down well with a lot of persons mostly in health and economic benefits. Ihedioha (2017) from different perspective disengagement may not need to be viewed as outward behaviour of individual, but may refer to as inner attitude towards life.

Activity and Continuity of Aliening

This theory is saying that active activity gives satisfaction in life, our perception of ourselves helps us to reason and think in a view of working it out. At old age some early persons are active because of their early foundation, and human wants about life and its (satisfaction) desires of the time. Maintaining of a class of personality makes them to work harder.

In Nigeria aging is perceived as a burden especially and to family members, as the country has failed to provide financial help of benefit from the abundance of experience that comes with old age in the form of wise counsel in the resolution of conflicts of crises in the community. Thus, this reminds the Nigerian government of the social policies which she is supposed to provide to serve the citizen and justify their existence. However, the burden of care for the elderly squarely rests on family members despite the provisions made in the 1999 constitution SECTION 14.2 (b) of the constitution: states that the security and welfare of its people shall be the purpose of the government, and it provides in section 16, sub-section 2 (d), that suitable and adequate food, reasonable national, minimum unemployment as well as sick benefit; federal government of Nigerian 1999 P (12). Unfortunately, the Nigeria government seems not to have kept to this social contract and has reneged on this promise as most elderly people are not covered by any social policy within the new planned social security schemes, but instead has opted for the creation of employment opportunities for the youth. The introduction of neo-economic policies has brought to the front burner, the hopelessness of the poor and elderly in Nigeria (Mbah, 2014).

Abuse of the Aged in Nigerian

Gerald, & others (2005), the general public endorses many mistaken beliefs about elderly. Raising from sex, appetite, physically fitness, exercise mode of dressing. The physical realities of aging are complicated by ageism, which can be defined as discrimination against any person, young or old. Based on chronological age, ageism can be seen when a professor who is in his/her sixties is considered too old to teach. Or in social gatherings a man of seventy years is not considered to grace an occasion that he or she is not the celebrant or not related to the family of the celebrant.

In many discussions of the differences between the old and the not yet old. The old are usually defined as those over the age of 65 years. The decision to use this age was set largely by social policies, not because of age 65 is some critical point of which the physiological and psychological processes of aging suddenly begin. WHO (2002) it is the elderly people with a mental disorder many suffer from double jeopardy- that is, they suffer the stinging associated of being older and being mentally ill. Unfortunately, almost no research has explored stinging associated with mental illness among older adults.

It is important to note that in addition to life if exposure to losses and to other stressors, older adults have many positive life experience, coping, mechanism, and wisdom on which to draw. Moreover, older adults who belong to groups that provide meaningful, strong roles for them seem to have an easier time adjusting to growing. Knight (1996), Setin (1982) in Gerald el (2005) a study therapist in Canada and United States were provided with a description of people various ages with personality disorder requiring treatment. The result showed that therapist overwhelmingly preferred to provide treatment to middle-aged and younger adults than to the elderly. Psychotherapist were less likely to respond this way if they themselves were older adults, or had taken three or more professional courses focusing on older adults, or had practices in which at least one in 10 of their clients was 65 or older. The views of psychotherapist are paralleled by equally negative views of the elderly endorsed by people in the general population. Some people pay less attention to the elderly.

Let us look at the following on the elderly.

Financial: This is one of the problems that the aged faces, his money, assets, both landed property and other investments may be abused by wife, children and relations.

Neglect: The elderly may not be given water to bath. Food, his room will not be kept clean either by wife and children or caregiver etc.

Psychological or Emotional Abuse: This can occur in so many ways i.e. screaming or yelling, insults, threatens, intimidates, denial of privacy or removes the power of the elderly to make decisions.

Physical Abuse: This entails infliction of fair discomfort or injury (e.g. the elderly show physical signs of possible abuse such as, swollen grips, marks of violence or fractures.

Sexual Abuse: The abuse is of a sexual nature (e.g. an elderly person is sexually assaulted or abuse by a neighbor).

Attitude of the paramilitary towards the elderly may not be really reported by the victim in this part of the world.

Mistreatment of the Elderly

Mistreatment of the elderly may fall under of the four categories.

1. Physical violence intended to cause injury.
2. Psychological or emotional abuse, which may include insults and threats; such as the threat of abandonment, or institutionalization.
3. Material exploitation, or misappropriation of money or property.
4. Neglect- intentional or unintentional failure to meet a dependent older person's need physical violence may be less common than is generally believed.

The American medical association (1992) added the fifth (5) category: violating personal right for example, the older person right to privacy and to make her on his own personal and health decisions. Contrary to popular belief, most elderly abuse does not occur in the institutions where there are laws and regulations to prevent it. It most often happens to frail or demented elderly people living with spouses or children.

The abuse is more likely to be a spouse since older people live with spouse Lachs & Pillemer (1995). This is always a continuous matter. Elder abuse should be recognized as a type of domestic violence, most physical abuse can be resolved by counseling or other services **AARP** (1993) Abusers need treatment to recognize what they are doing and assistance to reduce the stress of care giving because the needs and human rights of older adults have become an international concern.

Social emotional selective theory "Carstensen" '1996' older adults become increasingly selective about the people with whom they spend their time, when people perceive their remaining time as short, immediate

emotional needs take precedence over long range goals. A college student may be willing to put up with a disliked teacher for the sake of gaining knowledge to get into graduate school, an older adult may be less willing to spend precious time with a friend who gets on her nerves. Young adults with a free half hour and no urgent commitments may choose to spend the time with someone, they would like to get know better, older adults tend choose someone they know well. Even though the older, the fewer your social network is, the older tend to be satisfied with the few they have.

Research Questions

1. What percentage of Nigerian police have positive and negative attitude towards the elderly?
2. What is the attitude of male and female police towards the elderly?

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference between Nigeria police with positive and negative attitude towards the elderly.
2. There is no significant difference between the attitude of male and female police towards the elderly.

Limitations

This is a new area in research, ‘‘the aged’’ which has caused the researcher a lot of stress and money to gather information and documents which were not available and it worthy to recommend further research to encourage our institutions to keep a record of any contact with the elderly in their institutions.

Methods and Procedure

The data for this work came out as a result of interviews, and filling of questionnaires b police officers. There was an oral interview with the divisional crime officer of Nkpolu Police Division **SP DENNIS GBURUGBARA**- he said that elderly persons are not abused but respected and attention are always given to them. The **2/C Legal State CID Port Harcourt**. He is a lawyer and police prosecutor **DSP Samuel Njoku** now at Bayelsa – head of Police Lawyer Yenagoa (SIID). He is knowledgeable in the prosecution of criminal cases reports to the commissioner of police, he said elderly cases are always given urgent attention.

The area commander **Bori ACP Ekaette Archibong**, - Assistant Commissioner of Police said that elderly persons are always treated as senior citizens on any matter that they appear or report, but she advised that they should not allowed to be coming to the police station alone to avoid being ill or having any attack as a result of their age because they are always at the station for cases of land matter, chieftaincy dispute, and other related matters. Relatives should always accompany the elderly to pursue their interested cases.

There was also a questionnaire for the officers that are always on the receipt of complaint from the public who are always at the charge room, on how they treat the elderly as they come to report the cases, randomly distributed and was retained through the Station Officer (S/O).

Result Presentation

Research Question 1: What percentage of Nigeria police have positive and negative attitude respectively towards the elderly?

Table 1: Attitude of Nigeria Police towards the elderly

Attitude	Number	Percentage
Positive	101	51.0
Negative	97	49.0
Total	198	100.00

Table 1 shows that 51.0 percent of the Nigeria police have positive attitude towards the elderly while 49.0 percent have negative attitude towards the elderly. The result is that only moderate number of the Nigeria police have positive and negative attitude towards the elderly.

Research Question 2: What is the attitude of male and female police towards the elderly?**Table 2: Attitude of male and female police towards the elderly**

Attitude	Female		Male		Total
	n	%	n	%	
Positive	22	44.0	80	54.1	102
Negative	28	56.0	68	49.9	96
Total	50	100.00	148	100.00	198

Table 2 indicated that 44.00 percent of the female police have positive attitude towards the elderly while 56.0 percent have negative attitude. The result is that slightly above average number of female police have negative attitude. The table also shows that 54.1 percent of the male police have positive attitude towards the elderly while 45.9 percent have negative attitude. The result is slightly above average number of male police have positive attitude towards the elderly. The indication is that more of male police compared to females have positive attitude towards the elderly.

HO¹: There is no significant difference between Nigeria police positive and negative attitude towards the elderly.

Table 3: Chi-square analysis of percentage difference between positive and negative attitude towards the elderly.

Attitude	O	E	DF	Chi-square (x)	Sig.	Decision
Positive	101	99	1			
Negative	97	99	17.13	0.081	0.776	NS
Total	198	198			100.00	

NS= Not significant of 0.05 level of significance

Table 4 is a summary of the chi-square test on whether there is no significant difference between Nigeria police positive and negative attitude towards the elderly. The calculated chi-square (x^2) was 0.081 which has a significant value of 0.776 which is higher than the chosen level of significance (0.05) and thus not significant. This implies that the null hypothesis stated is hereby not rejected. The result shows that there is no significant difference between the percentage Nigeria Police positive and negative attitude towards the elderly respectively.

HO²: There is no significant difference between the attitude of female and male police towards the elderly.

Table 4: t-test Analysis of female and male police attitude towards the elderly.

Gender	N	X	SD	DF	t	Sig.	Decision
Female	50	34.00	4.95				
				196	-0.670	0.503	NS
Male	148	34.53	4.84				

NS= Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Table 5 shows that the calculated t-value (0.670) at df 196 has a significant value of 0.503 which is greater than the chosen level of significance (0.05). The null hypothesis is therefore not rejected. The result shows that there is no significant difference between the attitude of female and male police towards the elderly.

Conclusion

Moderate number of Nigeria police showed positive and negative attitude towards the elderly. No significant difference in the attitude of female and male police.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations is made;

- Older persons should benefit from the family, community care and protection according to the norms and values of the society system and cultural values.
- They should be given free medical health care. They should also have free legal services at any point in time.
- Those issues affecting their rights and social affairs should be treated urgently to avoid depression. They should have access to appropriate institutional care providing protection, rehabilitation and social, mental stimulation in an appropriate environment. All fundamental human rights should be enjoyed by the elderly as long as they like.
- Older persons should enjoy the dignity of labor and social security. They should be distance from exploitation, physical or mental abuse or torture.
- Everyone should be treated equally irrespective of religion, background and education, sex or gender.

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POLICE ATTITUDE TOWARDS THE ELDERLY QUESTIONNAIRE (PATEQ)

Dear Respondent,

This questionnaire is designed to elicit data information on attitude of police towards the elderly. Please you are expected to respond honestly as instructed.

SECTION A: PERSONAL INFORMATION

Sex: Male Female

Years in Service: 1-5 6-10 11-15 16-20+

Rank: Constable Corporal Sergeant Inspector

SECTION B: POLICE ATTITUDE TOWARDS THE ELDERLY

Below are some scales on which we would like to rate your behaviour towards the elderly. Please rate each on the extent to which you agree by ticking (√) in the appropriate column.

Key: SA= Strongly Agree, A= Agree, D= Disagree, SD= Strongly Disagree, D= Disagree, SD= Strongly Disagree.

Police Attitudinal Scale (PAS)

S/NO	STATEMENTS	SA	A	D	SD
1	The elderly are usually kept waiting whenever they come to report assault cases.				
2	Little or no attention is given to the elderly at the counter in police stations.				
3	The elderly need to drop ‘‘something’’ to receive attention.				
4	When an elderly person is kidnapped, a swift action is taken.				
5	Any matter involving the elderly is given adequate attention.				
6	Kidnapped elderly people are given special treatment after being released by abductors				
7	Elderly ones are treated with love and care when found wandering or staying away from home				
8	Most police officers ignored the elderly involved in accident to save younger person instead				
9	Police officers empathize with a defrauded elderly person.				
10	If an elderly’s money is recovered by the police, he must part with a percentage of the recovered money as fine.				
11	The elderly deserve to be detained whenever arrested.				
12	The elderly should not be kept in the same cell with younger suspects.				
13	The elderly must be rushed to the hospital when sick in police custody				
14	The police must wait for elderly suspects relative to take them to hospital when ill				